

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP 2, Improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

D2.6 Report on data sources for reported pregnancies and handling processes

Lead contributor	A. Alexe; Novartis Pharma GmbH ; E.P. van Puijenbroek, Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb
Other contributors	L. Yates; KRISP, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Institute of Genetic Medicine, Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust M. Swertz, E. Hyde; University Medical Centre Groningen M. Partyka, Pfizer S. Kaplan, teva L. Greener, teva

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	18-10-2024	First Draft
V1.0	06-12-2024	Final version
V1.1	9-7-2025	Minor administrative revisions

Abstract

The ConcePTION project aimed to create a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data catalogue focused on medication use in pregnant and breastfeeding women. This catalogue was intended to make relevant datasets accessible to researchers and regulators by systematically documenting primary data sources. It was a critical step toward managing fragmented and underused datasets related to pregnancy and lactation. For collecting this information, a metadata model was developed to standardize data collection of primary data sources, as outlined in Deliverable 2.2 of Work package 2. Unfortunately the development of the catalogue faced significant technical challenges, including issues with data entry and extraction. In addition, in the pilot phase fewer participants contributed data than expected. As a result, the development process stalled. Although the MOLGENIS team provided a new WP2 catalogue, it was decided not to use this solution because another practical solution emerged with the implementation of the HMA-EMA catalogues, that turned out to be aligned with ConcePTION's goals. The catalogues were already integrated into established systems and scientists were already familiar with these EMA catalogues. For this reason, the ConcePTION team decided that developing an additional, parallel catalogue would not provide much added value. This report outlines the development challenges and the considerations that led to the decision to adopt the HMA-EMA catalogues as a suitable alternative solution.

Content

Content

Document History	2
Abstract	3
Introduction.....	5
Development of the Data catalogue	6
Identification of relevant data sources.....	6
Existing catalogues	6
Development Data-catalogue	6
Pilot	7
Discontinuation on development of data-catalogue.....	9
Characteristics of the HMA-EMA catalogue.....	10
List of abbreviations.....	11
References	12

Introduction

A central aspect of the ConcePTION initiative is the creation of a framework that includes a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable) data catalogue on data sources in which data have been specifically collected for the purpose of assessing the use of medications in pregnant and/or breastfeeding women. The development of an online, searchable catalogue was considered crucial for making these datasets visible and accessible to researchers and regulators in a timely manner. The catalogue would involve the systematic identification and documentation of primary data sources and would contain information on data sources with standardized workflows and tools to ensure analytical quality. It was considered a vital step in the ConcePTION project's efforts to identify, acquire, curate, store, manage, and govern currently fragmented and potentially underutilized datasets on pregnancy and lactation.

As a first step a meta data model of variables to be captured in the catalogue aimed at the collection of primary data was created, which was to be built into the ConcePTION data source catalogue. This model has been described in Deliverable 2.2 "Report describing the metadata model (variables) for data collection on pregnancy data sources".

The development and construction of the data catalogue was marked by several technical challenges. After the completion of the data model, a first version of the application was built, in which owners of the various data sources could enter their data. However, multiple problems emerged during the pilot phase. Both data entry and extraction procedures were not immediately functioning properly. These problems could ultimately not be solved in a timely and satisfactory manner and led to a significant delay. In addition, during the pilot phase it showed that the number of participants willing to enter their data fell short of expectations. Moreover, sustaining a WP2 catalogue next to WP7 catalogue is not a sustainable solution, while the WP7 catalogue development has led to major contributions to HMA-EMA catalogue (making WP7 and HMA-EMA catalogues similar).

Therefore a practical solution was found in the fact that the European Medicines Agency launched this HMA-EMA Catalogue for real-world data sources, studies, institutions and networks, well integrated into existing structures and enhanced the previous EU PAS Register and ENCePP Resource Database, which scientists were already familiar with. Moreover, it fitted well with the ideas within the ConcePTION project about the need and requirements for such data collection. As a result, the development of an additional ConcePTION WP2 data catalogue alongside the existing HMA-EMA catalogues no longer had much added value.

In this report, we describe the development of the WP2 data catalogue, our experiences in the pilot phase and the choices made to arrive at a workable, alternative solution.

Development of the Data catalogue

The design of the catalogue’s metadata model took into account both the structure and content of already existing data collections. To ensure the catalogue would serve as a valuable reference, the metadata model also captured key characteristics of pregnancy and/or lactation exposure datasets. This included not only the dataset’s location and ownership but also details on essential clinical variables, outcomes, and the data formats used. Additionally, the provenance of the data—documenting the sources, systems, and processes influencing the data—would be recorded, as well as information on data storage, handling processes, access, and governance. The following topics were addressed in the metadata model:

1. Aspects describing the source as a whole and its datasets
2. Variables and data formats enabling the identification of information
3. Provenance of data
4. Storage, handling processes and governance of the data of the various resources

More details of the model can be found in Deliverable 2.2. [1]

The catalogue would include a private negotiation service for arranging data access, along with a separate, secure platform for basic analysis of data characterization tables. This platform would have been utilized for feasibility assessments, accessible only after authentication. Lead beneficiary for the development of the prototype of the data catalogue was BBMRI-ERIC.

Identification of relevant data sources

The catalogue would encompass datasets related to human pregnancy and lactation, from sources such as regulatory agencies, industry, teratology information services, and drug or disease registries. These datasets include both prospectively reported pregnancy exposures and retrospective case reports, such as spontaneous reports. Additionally, incidental case reports of exposed pregnancies gathered from other sources would be included. Public institutions and pharmaceutical companies were contacted to provide detailed information on their relevant data sources, architecture, and collection processes via a structured electronic survey.

Existing catalogues

Several basic inventories have been created in the past, documenting data collections, such as the EUROMediSAFE inventory and the EMA inventory [2,3]. The EUROMediSAFE inventory dates from 2018 and concerns available data sources in all 28 EU Member States for potential use when evaluating the perinatal and long-term childhood risks associated with in-utero exposure to medication.[2] However, at the start of the project, both inventories had not recently been updated and offered limited search capabilities. To prevent duplication and to establish a single, trusted repository, the aim was to integrate characteristics from these existing data sources into the metadata model of the ConcePTION data source catalogue as far as possible.

Development Data-catalogue

The development of the data catalogue was based on the requirements, described in Deliverable 7.1 “User requirements and meta-data model for the FAIR data catalogue from WP1, 2 & 7 - task 7.4”. the catalogue included a database with the possibility of importing and exporting data. Data collection was based on electronic surveys sent to institutions or organisations that were known to maintain data sources.

In the initial phase, we discovered that the survey was not well-suited for easily collecting data across multiple pregnancy cohorts. Organizations with multiple data sources were required to complete multiple surveys, which complicated the data collection process. Due to the time-consuming and complex nature of the data entry, a paper version of the questionnaire was created as an additional reference tool. Users could download this version to preview the questions in advance. However, all questionnaires ultimately had to be completed online.

During the development of the data catalogue multiple logistical and technical issues were encountered. Navigation with the survey showed to be complex and error prone. Throughout the years, several technical issues arose due to server crashes and frequent intermittent outages. Initially, these problems were temporarily resolved, but eventually they became unmanageable. Unfortunately, it was not possible to identify the root cause of the failures. In April 2023, WP2 2 was notified that the database had been corrupted. The software developer managed to recover data from the original server, and a testing server was created. While the testing server was functional, it became apparent that some data was lost. Unfortunately, the extent of the loss could not be determined, as no previous snapshot of the database was available.

Our plan was to test access to the production environment once it became functional again and then resume sending out requests and follow-ups. After completing this round of requests, given the ongoing server issues and the sustainability concerns remained. Additionally, we observed that, although access to the catalogue appeared to be functional for contributors, in practice it was not working as expected.

By the end of 2023, efforts were made to restore functionality in order to conduct a second wave of requests to pregnancy cohort owners. However, several significant issues emerged, including missing previously entered data, malfunctioning access, unresolved causes of intermittent crashes, and a lack of sustainable support to address these problems. Although our IT colleagues were informed of the latest issues and were working on potential solutions, these challenges remained a major concern. WP2 colleagues sent approximately 150 requests to potential pregnancy cohort owners, but the response rate was notably low. We were uncertain if this was due to technical issues with accessing the platform or for other reasons.

An alternative platform on which the catalogue could be rebuilt was identified by Molgenis, however its use was considered not to be appropriate for the necessary data to be collected. No data import was possible between the two databases. Additionally, the functionalities were considered to be insufficient for the purpose of the data catalogue. This option was not further pursued by the team.

Pilot

Data source owners, were identified [Amalia, can you elaborate how this was done – list of those that were invited to be added as supplementary material?] to enter their registries or studies in the catalogue.

ConcePTION members with potential data sources in pregnancy and breastfeeding were invited to join the data catalogue by answering the questionnaire. In addition, literature searches were conducted to identify potential data sources for pregnancy and breastfeeding cohorts. The literature search strategies consisted of complex data searches in Pubmed. To identify potential data sources for pregnancy cohorts, the following strategy was used in Pubmed:

PubMed string:

((Ectopic pregnancy)OR(Spontaneous abortion)OR(Elective termination)OR(Miscarriage)OR(Still birth)OR(Fetal death)OR(Pre-term live birth)OR(Premature birth)OR(Neonatal death)OR(Congenital malformation)OR(Congenital anomaly)OR(Major congenital malformation)OR(Major congenital anomaly)OR(Fetal anomaly)OR(Birth defect)OR(Congenital abnormalities)OR(Postpartum haemorrhage)OR(Preeclampsia)OR(Congenital heart defect)OR(Neonatal Intensive Care Unit)OR(Infant Small for Gestational Age)OR(Low Birth Weight)OR(Small for Gestational Age)OR(Very Low Birth Weight)OR(Extremely Low Birth Weight)OR(Long term development outcome)OR(Attention deficit)OR(Autism spectrum)OR(Developmental delay)OR(Abnormal birth)OR(Post-term birth)OR(Small for gestational age)OR(Intrauterine growth retard)OR(Malformation)OR(Fetal death)OR(Abortion)OR(Stillbirth))

AND

((maternal exposure)OR(pregnancy exposure)OR(drug exposure during pregnancy)OR(exposure via placenta)OR(drug exposure in utero)OR(maternal drugs affecting fetus)OR(drug exposure via mother)OR(Complications of maternal exposure to therapeutic drugs)OR(foetal exposure)OR(exposure during pregnancy))

Hits were further restricted to: Human use, publications between 2009 and 2020.

To identify potential data sources for breastfeeding safety data, the Pubmed string was modified to:
 ((((((exposure via breast milk) OR (drug exposure via breast milk)) OR (breast milk odour abnormal)) OR (intoxication by breast feeding)) OR (breast milk discolouration)) OR (breast milk discoloured)) OR (maternal exposure during breast feeding)

The results for both literature searches were included as Appendices (Appendix A and B). All hits were reviewed by two WP2 members using article titles and abstracts, so that the potential source data holders are identified. Subsequently, the targeted contact details were extracted and the invitation to join the WP2 Data Catalogue was sent (Appendix C).

In parallel, the database using a Molgenis platform, was built in collaboration with Molgenis.

- The instructions to join the database is attached as Appendix D.
- The content of the questionnaire embedded in the database is attached as Appendix E.

The interface of the Data Catalogue database was designed to be user friendly. Additionally, users were able to filter the information included. Snapshots are included below:

The screenshot shows the 'ConcePTION' data catalogue interface. At the top, there are navigation links: Catalogue Data, Edit/View Survey, Overview Survey, Privacy Statement, Admin, Account, Help, and Sign out. The main content area displays a table of data items under the heading 'Data'. The table has columns for Organisation, Region covered, Starting year, End year, and Total number of records. A tooltip is visible over the 'Region covered' column, asking for details of the region covered.

Organisation	Region covered	Starting year	End year	Total number of records
TIS Zerfin, Israel - Drug Consultation Center				50000
The Israeli Teratology Information Service, Jerusalem				356569
UK Teratology Information Service	Country	1978		60000
Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Center Lareb	Country	2014		5000
Rotunda Hospital	Country	2017		70000
Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Center Lareb	Country	1999		1400

SWISS TERATOGEN INFORMATION SERVICE	
Acronym: (STIS)	
GENERAL INFORMATION ON SPONTANEOUS REPORTS	
Region covered	Country
Starting year	1975
Total number of reports	10000
Number of reports per year	400
Reporter to database	Healthcare Providers
Dedicated Report	Yes
Document related to lactation	Yes
Data used	Answering patient specific clinical enquiries Characterising the safety profile of use in pregnancy Peer reviewed scientific publications To fulfil regulatory requirements

Additionally, functionality to extract reports with the data included was added. An example is added below:

A	B	C	D	E	F	
Organisation	Region covered	Starting year	End year	Total number of reports	Number of reports per year	Reporter to database
Swiss Teratogen Information Service	Country	1975		10000	400	Healthcare Providers
Novartis Pharma AG	Worldwide	1961		5000000	1100000	Healthcare Providers,
Medical center for drug safety in pregnancy and lactation		2009		1300	200	Healthcare Providers,
Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb		1991		316644	30000	Healthcare Providers,

Even though initially the database has worked well, in 2022 technical issues started to occur, to the point that the data catalogue was no longer available for the ConcePTION users. These were solved by the Molgenis data point each time they were occurring; however the source of the issues was not identified. It was hypothesized that incomplete data in the reported questionnaires could cause the system to crash. The technical issues have been intermittent, until 2023, when the system froze completely. The IT support team was contacted, however they have informed that the database is unusable and data cannot be retrieved.

At that point, invitations to join the data catalogue were already sent and responses started to arrive. No data could be recovered except for reports previously extracted by WP2 members in 2021, including only 8 sources.

An alternative platform on which the catalogue could be rebuilt was identified by Molgenis, however its use was considered not to be appropriate for the necessary data to be collected. No data import was possible between the two databases. Additionally, the functionalities were considered to be insufficient for the purpose of the data catalogue. This option was not further pursued by the team.

Discontinuation on development of data-catalogue

Due to the aforementioned, unforeseen technical issues, the development of the catalogue had to be discontinued. In particular because Conception WP7 developed a new catalogue, which has become a foundation of European Medicines Agency development of a similar catalogue in recent years (via Conception partners who joined EMA Minerva project[4,5]). A practical solution therefor is to move to this new HMA-EMA catalogue, in particular when it was recognized that the EMA has been working on migrating the ENCePP Resource Database to the new Catalogue of real-world data (RWD) sources, creating a centralized repository for RWD sources. These catalogues assist medicine regulators, researchers, and pharmaceutical companies

in identifying the most appropriate data sources for specific research questions, as well as supporting the evaluation of study protocols and results. Their goals are to enhance transparency, promote the use of best practices, and foster trust in non-interventional research.

In early 2024, after consultation with the Project Management Office and the catalogue development team, it was decided that the data source catalogue had to be discontinued. This was partially driven by technical difficulties, but also because a more sustainable and cost effective solution to address the need for a single repository of pregnancy studies has been identified.

Data source owners, identified via the catalogue task, were encouraged to enter their registries or studies in the new HMA-EMA Catalogue of real-world data sources

Characteristics of the HMA-EMA catalogue

The HMA-EMA catalogues for real-world data sources, studies, institutions, and networks were well integrated into existing systems and enhanced the EU PAS Register and ENCePP Resource Database, both of which were already familiar to scientists. The Catalogue of RWD sources has replaced the ENCePP Resources Database. Additionally, catalogues of institutions and networks have been introduced to complement the RWD sources and studies catalogues. Together, these catalogues provide an enhanced and more efficient service for researchers, regulators, and pharmaceutical companies by facilitating the discovery of suitable data sources to generate real-world evidence for regulatory purposes (e.g., identifying RWD sources relevant to specific research questions). These catalogue was able to support the assessment of data sources' by offering clear, easy access to information from study protocols and reports and enhancing interoperability between studies and data sources. The catalogues are fully searchable, and data from registered entities can be easily exported for further use. [6] Finally, the HMA-EMA catalogues aligned well with the ConcePTION project's objectives and requirements for data collection, as demonstrated by Conception members co-developing the design of the HMA-EMA catalogue in the Minerva project. Consequently, developing a separate ConcePTION WP2 data catalogue alongside the existing HMA-EMA catalogues no longer offered significant added value.

List of abbreviations

CDM Common Data Model

EMA European Medicines Agency

EU European Union

ENCePP European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance

FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable)

HMA Heads of Medicines Agencies

ICSR Individual Case Safety Report

MAH Marketing Authorization Holder

NA Not applicable

PV Pharmacovigilance

RWD Real World Data

WP Work package

References

- 1 ConcePTION website. D2.2 Report describing the metadata model (variables) for data collection on pregnancy data sources. <https://zenodo.org/records/5825112>
- 2 Gorki M, Morris J. Inventory of available data sources in all 28 EU Member States for potential use when evaluating the long-term risks for children associated with in-utero exposure. http://www.euromedicat.eu/content/EUROmediSAFE%20Inventory_Finalv2_2018_07_06.pdf
- 3 Charlton R, de Vries C. Systematic overview of data sources for drug safety in pregnancy research Consultancy EMA/2010/29/CN prepared for the European Medicines Agency, June 2012 updated for ENCePP June 2016. www.encepp.eu/structure/documents/Data_sources_for_medicines_in_pregnancy_research.pdf
4. Gini R, Pajouheshnia R, Gutierrez L, et al. Metadata for Data discoverability and Study replicability in observational Studies (MINERVA): Lessons Learnt From the MINERVA Project in Europe. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf* 2024;33(8):e5884. doi: 10.1002/pds.5884 [published Online First: 2024/08/15]
5. Pajouheshnia R, Gini R, Gutierrez L, et al. Metadata for Data discoverability and Study replicability in observational Studies (MINERVA): Development and Pilot of a Metadata List and Catalogue in Europe. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf* 2024;33(8):e5871. doi: 10.1002/pds.5871 [published Online First: 2024/08/15]
6. Website European Medicines Agency. HMA-EMA Catalogues of real-world data sources and studies. <https://catalogues.ema.europa.eu/> [date a

Appendix A – Literature search results for Pregnancy

WP2 Literature research on the use of medicinal products during breastfeeding

Project: **Conception**

Created Date: 24 December 2020

Author: Dave Lewis

Owner: Amalia Alexe

Document Ref: WP2-001-Literature review lactation

Version No: v0.1

Table of Contents

Document History	2
Document Location.....	2
Revision History	2
Approvals.....	2
Introduction	3
Method.....	3
Results.....	4
Discussion	4
Conclusions	4
Reference	4
Annex 1. Literature Review on the Use of Medicines During Location	5
Annex 2. Publications for Survey of Corresponding Authors	6

Document History

Document Location

This document is valid from the date of approval and only on the day it was printed, in case of up-versioning.

The source of the document will be found at this location –

Add WP2 SharePoint address with specific location

Revision History

Revision date	Previous revision date	Summary of Changes	Changes marked
04 Dec 2020	n/a	First issue for review by WP2 leaders.	Minor edits to Excel workbook.
31 Dec 2020	v0.1	Summary document and Excel workbook of results circulated for approval.	Clean copies of two files issued.

Approvals

This document requires the following approvals.

Signed approval forms should be filed appropriately in the project filing system.

Name	Signature	Title	Date of Issue
Laura Yates		WP2 Leader	
Eugène van Puijenbroek		WP2 Co-Leader	

Introduction

Scope and Purpose

This document provides an overview of the literature research focusing on the use of medicinal products by breastfeeding women, conducted on behalf of the IMI ConcePTION WP2 consortium.

Objectives

The objective of the research was to:

- Conduct a research of the literature related to the use of medicinal products during breastfeeding
- Identify important publications with the potential to provide information for further investigation within the IMI ConcePTION consortium
- Describe potential sources of further information, e.g. cohorts of patients available for further research by IMI ConcePTION

Method

PubMed® (1) was used for the literature research. This online retrieval system comprises more than 30 million citations for biomedical literature from MEDLINE, life science journals, and online books. PubMed was selected over other research tools because it offered more comprehensive filtering options for the required review.

Using the standard advanced search engine provided at PubMed.gov this search string below was generated:

(((((exposure via breast milk) OR (drug exposure via breast milk)) OR (breast milk odour abnormal)) OR (intoxication by breast feeding)) OR (breast milk discolouration)) OR (breast milk discoloured)) OR (maternal exposure during breast feeding)

Filters were then applied to limit the date of publication to between 2010 and 2020, to restrict the reports to include only use in humans, to limit to the English language, to focus on peer-reviewed journals & to exclude reports from interventional clinical trials:

Table 1. Search terms (lactation)

Lactation-associated reports: <i>Search terms</i>
(Drug) Exposure via breast milk
Breast milk odour abnormal
Intoxication by breast feeding
Breast milk discoloured
Maternal exposure during breast feeding

Table 2. Search Limits

Outline literature research strategy: <i>Limits</i>
Publications within 2010-2020
Human use
Language = English
Peer-reviewed journals
Exclude: interventional clinical trials

Results

One hundred and eighty (180) results were retrieved for review (see Annex 1). The citations retrieved included links to full-text content from PubMed Central and publisher web sites. Individual reference citations were accessed as required to verify the contents, either using abstracts or full-text.

Table 1.
Reports by publication year

2010	2
2011	17
2012	12
2013	21
2014	19
2015	18
2016	18
2017	16
2018	17
2019	37
2020	3
Grand Total	180

Discussion

This literature research yielded a very small number of significant reports, with only ten major reviews being published over a decade. On average this equates to the publication of only one review of the use of authorized medicines in breastfeeding women per calendar year. Aside of this there is a trend to report exposures and outcomes to individual medicinal products, which usually represents reporting at the instigation of the Marketing Authorisation Holder. Even here there is a focus on a very limited range of products, specifically anticonvulsants, nootropics including antidepressants and antipsychotics, anti-infectives particularly anti-retrovirals in HIV-positive mothers, narcotics and opioids).

Conclusions

In accordance with the aims of this literature research we will contact the authors for correspondence nominated in the ten review papers, inviting them to participate in the IMI ConcePTION survey, and to provide data to support and expand the ecosystem of data on the use of medicines during breastfeeding.

Reference

1. [Pubmed® was accessed @https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/.](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/)

Annex 1. Literature Review on the Use of Medicines During Lactation

Publications on use
of medicinal products

Annex 2. Publications for Survey of Corresponding Authors

PMID	Title	Authors	Citation	Year	DOI
21790831	Providing adequate directions for medication use in pregnant women and nursing mothers: an overview of pregnancy labeling	Corbett K, Kremzner M, Stifano T.	J Am Acad Nurse Pract. 2011 Aug;23(8):389-91. doi: 10.1111/j.1745-7599.2011.00641.x. Epub 2011 Jun 13.	2011	10.1111/j.1745-7599.2011.00641.x
21273359	Prescribing in pregnancy and during breast feeding: using principles in clinical practice	Henderson E, Mackillop L.	Postgrad Med J. 2011 May;87(1027):349-54. doi: 10.1136/pgmj.2010.103606. Epub 2011 Jan 27.	2011	10.1136/pgmj.2010.103606
22958026	Drugs and breastfeeding: instructions for use	Bertino E, Varalda A, Di Nicola P, Coscia A, Occhi L, Vagliano L, Soldi A, Perathoner C.	J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med. 2012 Oct;25 Suppl 4:78-80. doi: 10.3109/14767058.2012.715034.	2012	10.3109/14767058.2012.715034
23158505	Medication and breastfeeding	Varalda A, Coscia A, Di Nicola P, Sabatino G, Rovelli I, Giuliani F, Soldi A, Perathoner C, Bertino E.	J Biol Regul Homeost Agents. 2012 Jul-Sep;26(3 Suppl):1-4.	2012	
22614307	Drug use and breastfeeding	Nordeng H, Havnen GC, Spigset O.	Tidsskr Nor Laegeforen. 2012 May 15;132(9):1089-93. doi: 10.4045/tidsskr.11.1104.	2012	10.4045/tidsskr.11.1104
25455573	Maternal medication, drug use, and breastfeeding	Rowe H, Baker T, Hale TW.	Child Adolesc Psychiatr Clin N Am. 2015 Jan;24(1):1-20. doi: 10.1016/j.chc.2014.09.005. Epub 2014 Nov 14.	2015	10.1016/j.chc.2014.09.005
28510297	Evaluation of the Safety of Drugs and Biological Products Used During Lactation: Workshop Summary	Wang J, Johnson T, Sahin L, Tassinari MS, Anderson PO, Baker TE, Bucci-Rechtweg C, Burckart GJ, Chambers CD, Hale TW, Johnson-Lyles D, Nelson RM, Nguyen C, Pica-Branco D, Ren Z, Sachs H, Sauberan J, Zajicek A, Ito S, Yao LP.	Clin Pharmacol Ther. 2017 Jun;101(6):736-744. doi: 10.1002/cpt.676.	2017	10.1002/cpt.676
28886401	Factors associated with breastfeeding maintenance for 12 months or more: a systematic review	Santana GS, Giugliani ERJ, Vieira TO, Vieira GO.	J Pediatr (Rio J). 2018 Mar-Apr;94(2):104-122. doi: 10.1016/j.jped.2017.06.013. Epub 2017 Sep 5.	2018	10.1016/j.jped.2017.06.013
31010565	Balancing the Use of Medications While Maintaining Breastfeeding	Datta P, Baker T, Hale TW.	Clin Perinatol. 2019 Jun;46(2):367-382. doi: 10.1016/j.clp.2019.02.007. Epub 2019 Apr 1.	2019	10.1016/j.clp.2019.02.007
30663176	Drugs in lactation	Verstegen RHJ, Ito S.	J Obstet Gynaecol Res. 2019 Mar;45(3):522-531. doi: 10.1111/jog.13899. Epub 2019 Jan 20.	2019	10.1111/jog.13899

Appendix B – Literature search results for Pregnancy

abortion)OR(Elective
 termination)OR(Miscarriage)OR(Still
 birth)OR(Fetal death)OR(Pre-term live
 birth)OR(Premature birth)OR(Neonatal
 death)OR(Congenital
 malformation)OR(Congenital
 anomaly)OR(Major congenital
 malformation)OR(Major congenital
 anomaly)OR(Fetal anomaly)OR(Birth
 defect)OR(Congenital
 abnormalities)OR(Postpartum
 haemorrhage)OR(Preeclampsia)OR(Conge
 nital heart defect)OR(Neonatal Intensive
 Care Unit)OR(Infant Small for Gestational
 Age)OR(Low Birth Weight)OR(Small for
 Gestational Age)OR(Very Low Birth
 Weight)OR(Extremely Low Birth
 Weight)OR(Long term development
 outcome)OR(Attention deficit)OR(Autism
 spectrum)OR(Developmental
 delay)OR(Abnormal birth)OR(Post-term
 birth)OR(Small for gestational
 age)OR(Intrauterine growth
 retard)OR(Malformation)OR(Fetal
 death)OR(Abortion)OR(Stillbirth))
 AND
 ((maternal exposure)OR(pregnancy
 exposure)OR(drug exposure during
 pregnancy)OR(exposure via
 placenta)OR(drug exposure in
 utero)OR(maternal drugs affecting

Row Labels	Count of Title
2011	233
2012	211
2013	199
2014	265
2015	232
2016	248
2017	290
2018	311
2019	312
2020	99
Grand Total	2400

Appendix C – Template used for invitationWP2 Data Catalogue

Dear Professor/Doctor/...X,

ConcePTION is an IMI funded international project that aims to improve the available information on medication use in pregnancy and/or breastfeeding. As part of this project we are creating a catalogue of existing datasets and existing initiatives relating to the collection of human pregnancy and breastfeeding exposure data around the world.

Through literature searches and use of networks within ConcePTION, we have identified that you or your organisation may have data on medication use in pregnancy and / or breastfeeding that was collected for the primary purpose of studying or monitoring maternofetal outcomes. If this is correct, we would like to include an overview of your dataset in the ConcePTION global catalogue of data sources.

This online, searchable catalogue will be openly accessible to regulators and researchers as a tool to rapidly identify existing or ongoing data collections that may be of relevance to addressing safety questions relating to the use of a specific medicine(s) during pregnancy or breastfeeding.

We would therefore like to invite you to create an entry in the ConcePTION Catalogue of global data sources. This can be done by accessing the catalogue online via the CASE REPORT SURVEY [INSERT LINK](#), registering, and entering the information directly. If needed, step by step instructions on how to do this are attached.

Secondly, if you are aware of any other data sources of relevance, we would be most grateful if you would please provide the name and contact details for these data sources in the excel spreadsheet attached. We will then follow this up.

If you have any questions in relation to this or require assistance, please do not hesitate to ask.

Thank you in advance for your support.

Kind regards

Dr Laura M. Yates & Dr David J. Lewis

Dr Laura M. Yates

MBChB, DRCOG, MRCPCH, PhD, CCT Clinical Genetics
Consultant Clinical Geneticist
Inkosi Albert Lethuli Central Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal
Honorary Senior Lecturer
KRISP, University of KwaZulu-Natal

Dr David J. Lewis

EU QPPV Head QPPV Office emailto: eu-eea.qp@novartis.com
Person Responsible for Regulatory Compliance (Medical Devices) emailto: prrc.eu-mdr@novartis.com
Senior Visiting Research Fellow, Dept. of Clinical & Pharmaceutical Sciences, Univ. of Hertfordshire
T +49 7762 82 3010
M +41 79 582 3859
david-1.lewis@novartis.com
Assistant: Fabienne Hubert, fabienne.hubert@novartis.com
Chief Medical Office and Patient Safety
Novartis Pharma GmbH
Oeflinger Strasse 44
D-79664 Wehr

Appendix D – Instructions to join databases

Login with ConcePTION catalogue

How to login:

1. Use blue button “With ConcePTION catalogue”
2. Redirected to BBMRI-ERIC gateway (for authentication).

Select your identity provider

or

your institutional account

A*STAR - Agency for Science, Technology and Research
AAF Virtual Home
Aalborg University
Aalto University
Aarhus School of Marine and Technical Engineering
Aarhus University

3. Choose LifeScience Hostel (if you are already registered use your Email and Password, and skip next steps). If you did not register yet, use the link “Don’t have

Life Science Hostel Login

Enter your email and password

Email

Password

Login

[Forgot your password? Change it here!](#)

[Don't have account? Sign up here!](#)

BBMRI-ERIC[®]

BBMRI-ERIC, Neue Stiftingtalstrasse 2/B/6, 8010 Graz, Austria

+43 316 34 99 17-0

contact@bbmri-eric.eu

Copyright © BBMRI-ERIC 2020

account? Sign up here!”.

Home | News & Events | Publications | FAQ | National Nodes | Contact

Registration

Please perform the confirmation below to continue

I'm not a robot

reCAPTCHA
Privacy - Terms

Name*

E-mail*

Repeat e-mail*

Password*

The password must have at least 8 characters and at least one letter and one digit.
Please avoid using accented characters. It might not be supported by all backend components and services.

Organization*

Submitted registrations

- When you click to register a new page opens and a pop-up to confirm that you are not a robot.
- Fill in registration form, and click Submit. Please use organisation email and not

Registration to the LifeScience Hostel

Name*

E-mail*

Email with verification link will be sent to provided email address.

Repeat e-mail*

Password*

The password must have at least 8 characters and at least one letter and one digit.
 Please **avoid using accented characters**. It might not be supported by all backend components and services.

Organization*

> Submit

private email adress.

- After clicking Submit, an email will be send to provided email (if mail is not in inbox, please check SPAM folder)
- In mail there is a link to confirm registration, click on it ann registration process is completed.

Email verification

Your email address was verified.

Continue >

Neue Stiftingtalstrasse 2/B/6
 8010 Graz, AUSTRIA

Phone: +43 316 34 99 17-0
 Fax: +43 316 34 99 17-99
 Mail: contact@bbmri-eric.eu

Imprint / Disclaimer

FAVOURITES

- How to collaborate with BBMRI-ERIC
- News & Events
- Brochures & Publications

HOW TO FIND US

Your Location...

QUICKLINKS

- Directory 3.1
- Negotiator
- National Nodes

FOLLOW US

- After registration return to [ConcePTION website](#), click blue button again.
- Select LifeScience hostel, (fill in email and password), a new page opens with

Acceptable Usage Policy form

You must agree to the following acceptable usage policies:

Organization / Virtual Organization **bbmri**
See the acceptable usage policy in version 1.0 here.

I agree with the acceptable usage policy

BBMRI-ERIC, Neue Stiftingtalstrasse 2/B/6, 8010 Graz, Austria +43 316 34 99 17-0 contact@bbmri-eric.eu
Copyright © BBMRI-ERIC 2020

- 'Acceptable usage policy' click and then a new page opens.
- Consent to releasing personal information to service ConcePTION catalogue. Everything is selected, if you don't want to consent every time, also click "Do not ask again". Submit by clicking "Yes, continue".
- After clicking 'Yes, continue' you will be redirected to ConcePTION catalogue, to fill in questionnaire or to browse results.
- For the survey click on "Population-based healthcare data survey" or "Case pregnancy reports survey" (displayed in the blue buttons).

The screenshot shows the "ConcePTION Catalogue" page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo and links for "Result survey", "Overview Survey", "Privacy Statement", and "Account". On the right, there are "Help" and "Sign out" buttons. The main content area has a large heading "ConcePTION Catalogue". Below the heading, there is introductory text about the project, followed by a paragraph explaining the mission. Below this, there are two blue buttons: "Case pregnancy reports metadata catalogue" and "Population-based healthcare data catalogue". At the bottom, there is another set of two blue buttons: "Case pregnancy reports survey" and "Population-based healthcare data survey".

Appendix E – Questionnaire content

Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance data survey

Organizational information

What is the name of your organisation?

Novartis Pharma AG

What is the nature of the organisation?

Marketing Authorization Holder

What is the short version of the name of your organisation (acronym)?

NVS

What type of data do you collect in your organisation?

Spontaneous Reports

Does your organisation collect data or are you only accessing data collected by other organisations?

Both collecting data combined with accessing data from other institutions

Characteristics Organisation

Characteristics Spontaneous Data Organisation

Who is the contact person for questions related to the content of the data?

David Lewis

Please provide the email address of this contact person

eu-eea.qp@novartis.com

What is the department of this contact person?

CMO & Patient Safety

If different from the above, who is the contact person for technical aspects regarding the data collection?

Bitra Rezaallah

Please provide the email address of this contact person

Bitra.Rezaallah@novartis.com

What is the department of this contact person?

CMO & Patient Safety

What is the region covered?

Worldwide

What is the starting year of coverage? (if applicable)

1961

What is the estimated total number of reports, not limited to pregnancy only, of the collection?

5000000

What is the number of reports per year?

1100000

Who is reporting to the database?

Healthcare Providers, Patients/Consumers, Regulatory agencies, Other

Please specify, Other reporter

Contractual Partners

Is there a dedicated spontaneous report form to collect information about exposures related to pregnancy?

Yes

Is there a dedicated spontaneous report form to document exposures related to lactation?

Yes

How are pregnancy and breastfeeding related data being used?

Answering patient specific clinical enquiries, Characterising the safety profile of use in pregnancy, Data use by third parties, Monitor use of medication in pregnancy, To fulfil regulatory requirements, Peer reviewed scientific publications, Other

Please specify, if Other is selected

voluntary PASS (company-sponsored PASS)

Variables

Variables of Spontaneous Data that are collected

What medicinal products are monitored by your institution?

All medications of a specific Marketing Authorisation Holder, Specific drug(s)

Please specify these medicines

*Medicines in the same therapeutic class are being monitored post-marketing;
Active comparators are closely monitored during clinical trials (pre- and post-marketing)*

Do you allocate a 'suspect medicine' when multiple medicines are used?

Yes, the assessor of the case, Yes, the person who reports the case

If yes, do you record co-medications?

Yes

Is a coding system for classification of drugs being used?

Yes, for all drugs

Please specify which coding system is used (e.g. ATC or other)

Company dictionary and ATC, Unique Device Identification (UDI) for medical devices

Do you collect information on dosing?

Yes

Is information on timing of exposure in relation to the duration of pregnancy collected?

Yes

Do you only register adverse outcomes?

no, also both 'healthy' breastfeeding and pregnancy outcomes

What other types of outcome do you collect?

APGAR score, Birthweight, Child health, Congenital malformations (genetic/chromosomal), Congenital malformations (major), Congenital malformations (minor), Developmental disorders in childhood, Gestational age, Head circumference, Height, Neonatal complications, Sex, Timing of diagnosis congenital malformation

What type adverse outcomes do you collect on death?

Elective termination of pregnancy, Infant, Maternal, Neonatal, Spontaneous abortion/miscarriage, Stillbirth

What type of adverse pregnancy outcomes do you collect on pregnancy complications?

Gestational diabetes, Gestational hypertension, Preeclampsia, Premature Rupture of Membranes (PROM)

What type of adverse pregnancy outcomes do you collect on delivery complications and child health?

Low birth weight, Neonatal complications, Preterm birth

What type of adverse breastfeeding outcomes do you collect?

Effect on breastmilk: Colour, Effect on breastmilk: Taste, Effect on infant, Effect on production of breastmilk, Developmental outcomes in childhood, Other

What other types of information do you specifically register for spontaneous reports?

Conception (natural/artificial reproduction techniques), Expected Day of Birth, Expected Day of delivery, Familial history of congenital malformations, Last Menstrual period, Maternal Age, Maternal Alcohol, Maternal Birthdate, Maternal Comorbidities, Maternal Disease specific measurement, Maternal Height/Weight > BMI, Maternal Obstetrical history, Maternal recreational drug use, Maternal Smoking, Prenatal Screening, Family history of learning or educational problems

Do you specifically register information on long term outcomes related to the development and health of the child for spontaneous reports?

Yes, both neurodevelopmental and health related outcomes

Coding and Classification

Coding and classification of Spontaneous Data

Do you use specific regulations/terminology/definitions for the outcomes you collect?

Yes

Please specify

MedDRA dictionary ICH M1, ICH E2B(R3), ICH M2, sent via an ESTR1 (Electronic Standards for Transfer of Regulatory

Information) Gateway (AS2 Standard)

Do you use a coding system for classification of outcomes?

Yes, MedDRA, Yes, ICD 10, Yes, ICD 9, Yes, SNOMED

Do you monitor the quality and completeness of the pregnancy data?

Yes

Is a data quality process in place and documentation of that process available?

Yes, KQIs are in place for case quality during processing of safety data and during medical review. All metrics are documented and retained.

Quality Data

Screening and data analysis of Spontaneous Data

Do you have a procedure in place to regularly check for potential safety signals?

Yes

Which signal detection methods do you apply for the evaluation of exposure during pregnancy or lactation?

Yes, disproportionality analysis using multiple statistical techniques (e.g: Empiric Bayes geometric mean, PRR, CHI Square), statistical trending techniques for increased frequency and increased severity. In addition, global introspection by expert reviewers (specialist safety physicians).

Which signal detection methods do you apply for the evaluation of long term outcomes?

Disproportionality analysis and global introspection.

Are pregnancy cases readily classified and readily to be extracted?

Yes

Are exposure during lactation cases readily classified and readily to be extracted?

Yes

Linkage to other datasources

Export of Spontaneous Data

Are spontaneous reports on either exposure during pregnancy or during lactation submitted to EMA (EudraVigilance)?

Yes

Are your spontaneous reports exported to Vigibase(the WHO ICSR database)?

Yes

Are your spontaneous reports exported to a National Pharmacovigilance Centre?

Yes

In case of export to other institutions, please specify

All Health Authorities where Novartis is MAH or where Novartis is Sponsor.

Usage of the data

Use by third parties of Spontaneous Data

Are data made available for third parties?

Yes

What is the procedure for obtaining data access?

Requests from Health Authority, information exchange as per Safety Agreements with Contractual Partners, DSMBs, Ethics Committees, IRBs, investigators.

Where can applications forms for data access be found?

Freedom of Information requests (e.g: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/mhra-requests-under-the-freedom-of-information-act-foia>)

How long does the process of getting permission to use the data generally take?

20 working days if your request is a Freedom of Information request; and 40 calendar days if you are making a request for access to your personal data under the Data Protection Act 1998.

Are there any instructions for using this data source?

FOI Act @ <https://ico.org.uk/media/action-weve-taken/decision-notice/2018/2258224/fs50690676.pdf>, see also: Transparency of the UK medicines regulator: auditing freedom of information requests and reasons for refusal @ <https://ebm.bmj.com/content/24/1/20>

Publications

Key Publications with these data

If possible, please provide some key publications using the data (max 10)

1. Geissbühler Y, Rezaallah B, Moore A. An alternative to product-specific pregnancy registries? PRIM; PRegnancy outcomes Intensive Monitoring. *Reprod Toxicol.* 2020;94:13-21. doi:10.1016/j.reprotox.2020.03.004
2. Geissbühler Y, Vile J, Koren G, et al. Evaluation of pregnancy outcomes in patients with multiple sclerosis after fingolimod exposure. *Ther Adv Neurol Disord.* 2018;11:1756286418804760. Published 2018 Nov 3. doi:10.1177/1756286418804760
3. Rezaallah B, Lewis DJ, Zeilhofer H-F, and Berg B-I. Risk of Cleft Lip and/or Palate Associated With Antiepileptic Drugs: Post-marketing Safety Signal Detection and Evaluation of Information Presented to Prescribers and Patients. *Therapeutic Innovation & Regulatory Science* 2018 1-10 <https://doi.org/10.1177/2168479018761638>
4. Rezaallah B, Lewis DJ, Pierce C, et al. Social Media Surveillance of Multiple Sclerosis Medications Used During Pregnancy and Breastfeeding: Thematic Qualitative Analysis. *Journal of Medical Internet Research.* August 2019. <https://doi.org/10.2196/13003>.

Technical information

Database for Spontaneous Report Data

What is the database structure?

Oracle

How often do you import the data?

daily

How long are data being preserved?

Lifetime of medicinal product, plus ten years

Do you keep updating the coding systems to the latest versions?

yes

Is the data model publicly available?

yes